

RESULTS OF THE INITIAL DATABASE PREPARATION STAGE FOR DEVELOPING GEOCHEMICAL SEARCH CRITERIA FOR RARE EARTH ELEMENT MINERALIZATION IN BLACK SHALES BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14557687>

Nowadays, in all sectors of human activity, in particular finance, economics, marketing, medicine and engineering the role of information is growing sharply, and this reason raises the demand for their effective manipulation, processing, and interpretation to study in various interests.

Today, a number of companies and research institutes are involving several scientific achievements and advanced technologies in order to improve the efficiency of work processes and to support successful discoveries. One of these approaches to make these jobs easier, more powerful, expected results more natural and less time-consuming to process large amounts of data is applying Artificial Intelligence (AI).

"Research on processing geochemical data and identifying geochemical anomalies has made important progress in recent decades. Fractal/multi-fractal models, compositional data analysis, and machine learning (ML) are three widely used techniques in the field of geochemical data processing. In recent years, ML has been applied to model the complex and unknown multivariate geochemical distribution and extract meaningful elemental associations related to mineralization or environmental pollution. It is expected that ML will have a more significant role in geochemical mapping with the development of big data science and artificial intelligence in the near future..." [1].

Moreover, in accordance with the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and to create favorable conditions for the accelerated introduction of artificial intelligence technologies and their widespread use in the country, the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan No. PP-4996 on February 17, 2021 came out.

Although there are not so much experience and literature, I strongly believe that involving new scientific trends such as Data mining (DM) and AI have a great impact on prospering of all directions of human life, in particular geoscience.

Geological information, including the different properties of rocks and the results for chemical elements are the object of applied geochemistry. And traditionally, these data are processed and geostatistically analyzed in order to study geochemical features such as the geochemical specializations of different rock groups, the determination of ore-generating chemical elements, and their various geochemical assemblies.

On the basis of these statistical studies, various geochemical maps (mono-element, additive, multiplicative) are built using methods like Kriging or Inverse distances to a power, in other words, maps of the halos of chemical elements.

Studying geochemical data that includes a wide range of chemical elements, it is difficult to determine objectively those geostatistical features listed above because of their complexity.

"This is because many exploration geologists rely upon the classical geostatistical method of Kriging which oftentimes do not produce accurate predictions due to the complexity of interactions between geological features and spatial variables" [2].

Based on these facts and arguments above, there is a great need to apply Data mining and Artificial Intelligence methods to geochemical research.

Therefore, I do research on applied aspects of geoscience, and advanced geological modeling on geochemical data, which helps to discover new perspective areas of deposits by developing research criteria of ore formations.

In the mineral industry and geological, especially geochemical research, and great enthusiasm for studying geological data, I attempt to pursue my dissertation on the topic: "Development of geochemical search criteria for rare earth element mineralization in black shales based on artificial intelligence" within my doctoral program.

To achieve the designated goal of developing geochemical search criteria, ICP-MS (61 elements) analysis results from over 7,000 samples taken from various mining workings (lithochemical sampling along primary halos, trenches, core drill holes, and adits) were used.

Initially, the Ustuk area database was prepared in MS Excel for processing in computer programs. Geostatistical analysis was mainly performed using Statistica 10 and QGIS, while geospatial analysis and geochemical mapping work was carried out using ArcGIS, QGIS, Global Mapper, and primarily Surfer 18 software.

In the initial stage, mainly using MS Excel, all chemical element laboratory analysis results (ICP-MS, 61 elements) were converted to the same unit of measurement (g/t). For results below laboratory analysis sensitivity or extremely high quantities, the lower and upper percentile (10%) values were mainly adopted. Samples with missing analysis results were removed from the database. As a result, from the initial 8,496 samples, 7,256 were retained for use in subsequent stages. In the next stage, coordinates were calculated for each sample from mining workings (lithochemical sampling along primary halos, trenches, core drill holes, and adits) needed for geospatial analysis. Samples in the database were categorized based on rock descriptions and rock-forming chemical elements.

Methodology and expected results:

Traditional and new approaches based on DM and AI of geostatic analysis will be performed and the necessary graphics (diagrams, halo maps, block diagrams) will be built.

In the next stages of the study, the results of both approaches (geostatistics parameters, geochemical patterns, geochemical halos, etc.) and the time spent and quality of the results are compared, and work on drawing conclusions is ongoing.

References:

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